

Summary of ESM2025 key research outputs

November 2025

INTRODUCTION

Human civilisation depends on interconnected Earth systems – such as the atmosphere, oceans, land and biosphere – for essentials like clean air, water, food and a stable climate. Earth system models (ESMs) provide an important scientific basis for understanding how human activity affects and is affected by these systems and are important for informing policy action, both for mitigation and adaptation to global climate change. However, certain questions around the design of strategies to pursue the goals of the Paris Agreement could still benefit from further development and improvement of ESMs.

ESM2025 – Earth system models for the future is a European research project on Earth System modelling that has built the next generation of European ESMs focussed on informing how efforts

to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (referred to as climate change mitigation) interact with our planetary Earth System. These models will help to provide valuable scientific insights to support successful implementation of the Paris Agreement.

The new models provide more complete and realistic representations of key Earth systems and their responses to human-caused emissions of greenhouse gases and land-use change. They will be able to provide essential scientific evidence for developing climate mitigation strategies as well as robust guidance on future global environmental risks, supporting policies targeting adaptation to global change.

The project ran from June 2021 – November 2025. This briefing provides a summary of the key improvements that have been made to Earth system models, the ways in which this will help to support policymaking and key findings from model outputs.

1. LAND MODELLING AND THE LIMITS OF LAND-BASED MITIGATION

Key Message

Land plays a central role in climate mitigation and adaptation. ESM2025 showed that land-based strategies can contribute to climate goals, but their effectiveness and side effects depend on how they are applied. The carbon sink potential of forests is less reliable than previously thought, and it becomes less effective as net-zero approaches. Other land uses, such as irrigation or intensive biomass cultivation, can also alter local climate, water availability, and food production.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Land is more than just a carbon sink. It actively shapes the climate through its influence on water cycles, surface temperatures, and the exchange of greenhouse gases with the atmosphere. ESM2025 improved how these processes are represented in Earth system models, allowing for a better understanding of the combined effects of land use, climate change, and mitigation efforts.

The project introduced more realistic simulations of how nutrient availability, especially nitrogen and phosphorus, limits plant growth and carbon uptake. It also improved how models represent emissions of methane, nitrous oxide, and organic aerosols from land. These developments helped provide a more complete picture of how land contributes to both climate warming and cooling.

ESM2025 researchers have also tested a range of land management strategies, including forestation, irrigation, energy crop deployment, and wood harvest. The results showed that the impacts of these strategies vary widely depending on where and how they are applied.

- In tropical regions, planting trees tends to cool the climate; in high-latitude areas, new forests can darken snowy surfaces and cause local warming, despite their CO₂ removal potential.
- Irrigation can lower land surface temperatures and increase humidity, but may reduce runoff and alter regional water availability.
- Large-scale bioenergy crops may help remove CO₂, but can also compete with food production and strain water resources.

The models also showed that the land's ability to store carbon may weaken over time, especially in warmer and drier conditions. This could make it harder to meet climate goals if too much reliance is placed on land-based removals.

Overall, ESM2025 highlighted that land-use strategies must account not only for carbon storage potential, but also for their wider impacts on food systems, water resources, and ecosystems. At the same time, the project revealed that current uncertainties in land carbon stocks can significantly alter estimates of land-use emissions and mitigation effectiveness. Addressing these risks requires better observations, improved model coordination, and more robust integration of land processes into climate planning.

2. INTERACTIVE METHANE MODELLING

Key Message

Methane is a powerful greenhouse gas and a major driver of near-term warming. ESM2025 improved how Earth system models represent methane by making them respond more realistically to both human and natural emissions, as well as to changes in the climate system. This makes it possible to better estimate the climate impact of global methane pledges.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Methane plays a crucial role in near-term climate warming, but until recently, the current generation of Earth system models treated it in a simplified way, prescribing atmospheric concentrations rather than simulating how emissions evolve and interact with climate.

ESM2025 took a major step forward by implementing interactive methane modelling in several Earth system models. The models now simulate methane sources and sinks dynamically, including emissions from wetlands, lakes, wildfires, and thawing permafrost – all of which are sensitive to temperature, moisture, and ecosystem change. These natural sources were previously underrepresented or static in many models.

The project also improved how methane interacts with atmospheric chemistry, especially its reaction with hydroxyl radicals (which determines methane's lifetime) and its contribution to ozone formation. These enhancements make it possible to run emission-driven simulations, where the models respond directly to methane emissions rather than relying on prescribed concentrations.

This combined approach allows researchers to assess how methane from both human and natural sources contributes to climate change. It also enables more accurate estimates of how fast methane reductions might cool the climate, or how feedbacks from natural systems could amplify warming. These capabilities are essential for evaluating methane pledges, preparing for the next CMIP cycle, and informing near-term climate strategies.

3. INTERACTIVE ICE SHEET MODELLING AND SEA LEVEL RISE

Key Message

Melting ice sheets are a major driver of long-term sea level rise. ESM2025 took an important step forward by improving how Earth system models can simulate ice sheets and their contributions to sea level. These advances help society better understand future risks linked to polar ice loss.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Ice sheets in Greenland and Antarctica contain enough frozen water to raise global sea levels by many metres. Their response to climate change remains one of the largest uncertainties in long-term sea level projections. Until recently, most Earth system models included only a simplified treatment of ice sheets or omitted them entirely.

ESM2025 made significant progress by enabling and improving the coupling of dynamical ice sheet models in two major European Earth system models: UKESM and IPSL-ESM. These enhanced models can now simulate how ice sheets evolve in response to climate forcing and how those changes feed back on the climate system and influence global sea level.

Although the sophistication of several aspects of this coupling still needs to be developed further, both models now include key processes such as surface mass balance (the net accumulation or melting of snow and ice), the dynamic flow of the ice sheet and melting where the ice meets the ocean. These models can now produce more realistic simulations of how polar regions respond to warming, especially under high-emission or overshoot scenarios where irreversible ice sheet instabilities may pose serious risks.

By developing ways in which Earth system models and ice sheet models can work together, ESM2025 laid the foundation for better understanding of feedbacks between ice, ocean, and climate and more accurate projections of sea level rise. These advances are critical for informing coastal adaptation planning and for identifying potential tipping points in the Earth system.

4. INTERACTIVE NITROGEN MODELLING

Key Message

Human-driven changes to the nitrogen cycle affect not only air and water quality but also how ecosystems absorb carbon. ESM2025 improved how Earth system models simulate nitrogen flows, including those from agriculture. These advances help anticipate future risks to food security, climate, and environmental sustainability.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Nitrogen is essential for plant growth, but its role in the Earth system is complex. Excess reactive nitrogen, especially from agriculture, contributes to pollution, biodiversity loss, and greenhouse gas emissions. At the same time, nitrogen availability limits how much carbon ecosystems can take up, influencing the strength of the land carbon sink.

ESM2025 improved nitrogen representation in Earth system models in two important ways.

First, the project advanced the coupling of terrestrial nitrogen cycles with land surface models. This allowed for better simulation of how nitrogen availability affects plant growth, carbon uptake, and the release of nitrous oxide (N₂O), a potent greenhouse gas. The models also included nitrogen released from thawing permafrost, which may temporarily boost ecosystem productivity but ultimately adds to warming.

Second, ESM2025 developed a new model for agricultural ammonia emissions, capturing emissions across all farm stages, from animal housing to fertilizer use. When applied to future livestock scenarios, the model projected a strong increase in global ammonia emissions by 2100 under certain pathways. These emissions influence both air quality and nitrogen deposition, which in turn affect ecosystems and climate feedbacks.

By linking nitrogen flows across ecosystems, agriculture, and climate processes, ESM2025 improves our ability to explore the trade-offs between food production, mitigation strategies, and environmental goals in future scenarios.

5. LAND-TO-OCEAN CARBON AND NUTRIENT TRANSPORT

Key Message

Rivers connect land and ocean, transporting carbon and nutrients that shape marine ecosystems and influence how much carbon dioxide the ocean absorbs. ESM2025 revealed dynamics that are often overlooked in Earth system models, with important consequences for estimating carbon budgets and regional climate feedbacks.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Earth system models have traditionally treated land and ocean carbon cycles as separate systems, often overlooking the transport of carbon and nutrients through rivers and coastal zones. Yet these flows play an active role in the climate system. As carbon moves from land to ocean, a significant share is released back into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide, especially in river networks and coastal waters. These transformations affect how much CO₂ the ocean can actually absorb and also influence oxygen levels and nutrient cycling in marine ecosystems.

ESM2025 improved how these land-to-ocean fluxes are represented in models, incorporating both natural processes such as erosion and organic matter runoff, and human-driven inputs including fertiliser and wastewater discharge. Crucially, the models now account for how much carbon is lost during transport, rather than assuming it all reaches and is stored in the ocean.

The findings show that neglecting these dynamics can lead to overestimates of ocean carbon uptake and a poor understanding of changes in coastal biogeochemistry and ecosystem functioning. Changes in land use and nutrient flows can also trigger delayed effects in the ocean that unfold over years to decades.

By integrating these flows, ESM2025 filled a critical gap in climate modelling. This leads to more realistic global carbon budgets and a better understanding of how land and ocean processes interact under future climate change.

6. OCEAN DYNAMICS

Key Message

The ocean is central to the climate system and enables life in marine ecosystems. It absorbs heat and carbon through physical and biogeochemical processes. ESM2025 improved how ocean models used in climate modelling represent the turbulent and convective oceanic motions, as well as the main marine biogeochemical cycles, making projections of global warming and ecosystem change more reliable.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

To project climate change reliably, Earth system models must accurately represent ocean dynamics (horizontal circulation and vertical motions), and biogeochemical cycling. These processes govern the transport of heat, carbon, oxygen, and nutrients, and shape how the ocean responds to and buffers climate change.

In ESM2025, researchers improved physical ocean processes in several global models used for climate projections. The project made the simulation

of ocean convection and eddies more realistic. These refinements enhanced the simulation of vertical heat and nutrient transport, stratification patterns, and large-scale circulation features that influence regional and global climate variability. In particular, models like CNRM-ESM showed reduced biases in sea surface temperature and subsurface structure when the representation of the eddy-induced circulation is improved.

At the same time, the project also advanced marine biogeochemical modelling. The representation of the carbon and nitrogen cycles has been improved. Model developments also refined simulations of marine emissions of greenhouse gases such as the nitrous oxide, which is influenced by ocean deoxygenation and marine nutrient dynamics.

These process-level developments are essential for increasing the realism of Earth system models. They strengthen the foundations for projections of sea level rise, ocean heat content, carbon storage, marine greenhouse gases emissions and climate feedbacks, and will support more robust simulations in future climate assessments.

7. WILDFIRE DYNAMICS

Key Message

Wildfires are increasing in many regions due to climate change, land use, and vegetation dynamics. ESM2025 improved how models simulate the wide-ranging effects of fires on the Earth system, including their impact on carbon emissions, air quality, and climate–ecosystem interactions. The project also explicitly included human drivers (e.g. ignitions, suppression, and land management) and showed that socioeconomic factors matter for future wildfire projections.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters

Wildfires are a powerful component of the climate system. They emit carbon dioxide, smoke, and other pollutants into the atmosphere. Fires also affect how sunlight is reflected at the surface, how vegetation recovers, and how much carbon ecosystems can store. These changes influence how the climate system responds over time.

ESM2025 improved how fire dynamics are simulated in Earth system models. The project strengthened the links between fire, vegetation growth, and carbon cycling, and explored how future fire patterns may change under different climate and land use conditions. It also advanced the representation of how fires affect vegetation resilience, carbon stocks, and air quality. In addition, ESM2025 implemented socioeconomic drivers (e.g., ignition pressure, suppression capacity, and land management) so wildfire modules respond to human as well as climatic-driven change.

These improvements make it possible to simulate more accurately how changing fire regimes interact with climate and ecosystems. They help reveal whether fire may amplify or dampen regional warming, and how smoke and particles from wildfires influence pollution and atmospheric processes.

By improving how fires are represented in Earth system models, ESM2025 supports better assessments of risks related to climate feedbacks, land management, and environmental health.

8. EMISSIONS PATHWAYS AND GLOBAL WARMING LIMITS

Key Message

Every tonne of CO₂ we emit adds to global warming – and stopping that warming means reaching net zero. ESM2025 improved the modelling tools used by academia, civil society, governments and the United Nations to estimate how much we can still emit while staying below 1.5 °C or 2 °C, including how non-CO₂ gases and Earth system feedbacks may shift the timing and scale of those remaining carbon budgets.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters:

A key insight from climate science is that global warming is closely linked to the total amount of CO₂ ever emitted. This simple and robust relationship underpins the concept of carbon budgets: the idea that there is a finite amount of CO₂ we can still emit to limit warming to 1.5 °C or 2 °C. ESM2025 helped confirm that this cumulative emissions approach remains reliable, but also revealed some important nuances.

The project used an improved version of the MAGICC model (OS-MAGICC), alongside other tools, to simulate how the climate system responds to different emissions trajectories. These experiments showed that:

- Achieving net-zero CO₂ is essential to halt global warming; emission reductions alone are not enough.
- Methane and nitrous oxide emissions also play a major role. Methane, in particular, is responsible for nearly half of today's warming, and if reduced, could actually lead to cooling.
- Unless non-CO₂ emissions fall substantially, remaining carbon budgets compatible with the Paris Agreement may already be exhausted.

ESM2025 also used model experiments to explore how the Earth system might respond after reaching net-zero emissions. The results confirmed that cumulative CO₂ emissions remain a strong predictor of long-term warming, but also revealed small deviations that may shift the timing of peak warming relative to when net zero is achieved.

In some cases, during extended periods of net-negative emissions, models showed surprising

ocean circulation responses. These could affect how much cooling is achieved per tonne of CO₂ removed, pointing to uncertainties in how the Earth system reacts under strong mitigation scenarios.

By improving how Earth system models estimate carbon budgets and account for complex feedbacks, ESM2025 supports more scientifically grounded and policy-relevant mitigation pathways, including those used in the next IPCC assessments.

9. ESM-IAM FRAMEWORK FOR POLICY-RELEVANT SCENARIO ASSESSMENT

Key Message

To make climate scenarios more realistic and useful for decision-making, we need to better connect Earth system science and socio-economic modelling. ESM2025 took an important step by bringing these two communities together within the same project, which helps ensure that emission pathways used in policy are physically consistent with how the Earth system actually responds.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters:

Climate policy relies on scenarios that combine socio-economic assumptions (like population, technology, and land use) with the physical response of the climate system. But in practice, these two elements – represented by Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) and Earth system models (ESMs) – often run separately, with simplifications or mismatches between them.

ESM2025 made substantial progress in developing a more integrated framework to bring ESMs and IAMs into closer alignment. This involved:

- Improving open-source tools (such as OS-MAGICC) that translate emissions into concentrations and vice versa,
- Working towards greater consistency between socio-economic pathways and ESM-compatible inputs, particularly for key variables like CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O.
- Applying the framework to explore a range of scenarios and model types, including simple climate models and selected ESM outputs.

ESM2025 research ensured that mitigation scenarios could be assessed using a scientifically consistent picture of how greenhouse gas emissions affect the climate, and how land-based mitigation strategies like afforestation or bioenergy may behave under future climate conditions. This helps improve the robustness of global carbon budgets, the credibility of climate projections, and the clarity of trade-offs between different mitigation pathways.

While no single model can capture all aspects of the Earth system or global economy, linking IAMs and ESMs helps combine their respective strengths, enabling more credible, transparent, and science-informed policy decisions. ESM2025 showed how such connections can support future IPCC assessments and national climate planning through improved comparability, traceability, and relevance of climate scenarios.

10. ROBUST MITIGATION STRATEGIES AND SCENARIO EVALUATION

Key Message

Not all climate mitigation strategies are equally safe or effective. Using the integrated framework developed by ESM2025 that links Earth system and integrated assessment models, the project helped identify which types of emissions cuts and carbon removal pathways are more likely to limit warming, and which ones carry risks, trade-offs, or unintended consequences. This improves our ability to design fair and feasible strategies to meet the Paris Agreement goals.

What ESM2025 Did and Why It Matters:

Climate pathways often rely on a mix of emissions reductions and carbon dioxide removal (CDR) to limit global warming. But not all CDR strategies work the same way, and their performance can depend on complex Earth system feedbacks, including how land, oceans, and the atmosphere interact under future climate conditions.

ESM2025 built the tools to create and evaluate a wide range of mitigation scenarios, with particular focus on the behaviour of land-based mitigation options (such as afforestation and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage – BECCS) under different warming pathways. The project found that:

- Land-based CDR strategies can reduce warming but also bring side effects (e.g. changes in albedo, water availability, or food production),
- Earth system feedbacks can make land-based mitigation much less effective – sometimes cutting the expected carbon-removal benefits by half.
- Awareness of these uncertainties lets us identify strategies that remain effective under a wide range of potential Earth responses.

By combining detailed Earth system modelling with scenario evaluation tools, ESM2025 helped clarify which mitigation strategies are most robust, meaning those that perform well across uncertainties, avoid reliance on risky assumptions, and align with multiple sustainability goals.

These insights support more responsible use of scenarios in climate policy, improve the scientific foundations for mitigation planning, and inform future work on designing fair, effective, and resilient climate strategies.

FURTHER INFORMATION

ESM2025 website: www.esm2025.eu

ESM2025 research (data, tools and publications): www.esm2025.eu/research/

ESM2025 Research Highlights:

- Modelling carbon fluxes from the land to the open ocean: www.esm2025.eu/loac/
- Modelling Ice sheets in Earth System Models: www.esm2025.eu/icesheets/
- Exploring methane emissions and mitigation strategies through Earth System Models: www.esm2025.eu/interactive-methane-2/
- From ESMs to IAMs: www.esm2025.eu/esm-iam-framework/
- Can we count on the land? Exploring the uncertainty of land-based mitigation strategies: www.esm2025.eu/landcdr/

ABOUT THE TEAM

Led by Météo France-CNRM, the project consisted of an interdisciplinary team of 21 partners from 7 countries across Europe (Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK) and Australia.

The project team was composed of Earth-System scientists and model developers, experts in machine learning and data-driven hybrid modelling, model evaluation and feedback analysis, as well as specialists in integrated assessment models, climate education and science-policy communication.

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